

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_4_2_4	
Title	Camera traps and species observations
Category	Environmental/Spatial
Purpose of the method	<p>Camera traps are motion-sensitive cameras used to monitor animal activity in an area without human intervention. Camera traps are non-invasive, long-term, and cost-effective data collection tools. Applications are: wildlife monitoring, biodiversity assessment, ecological studies, and health status of animal.</p> <p>Camera traps can measure/analyse: species presence, population sizes and/or densities of species, behaviour, habitat use, human impact.</p>
Effort in time	<p>Camera traps are usually deployed for a few months or longer. Results can be analysed once the camera traps (or SD cards) are collected from the field and analysed by eye with the help of AI (using Agouti) depending on the number of camera traps deployed, the specifics of how the cameras are set (how easily they are triggered), and the duration of the deployments (e.g., 12 cameras deployed for 3 months, should take 2 weeks for data analysis in Slovenia).</p>
Number of objects investigated	<p>Camera traps are active all hours of the day and can record hundreds or thousands of events over a few months, depending on animal activity and presence. Furthermore, multiple camera traps can be deployed in an area at the same time. E.g., in one study in Slovenia, with 12 cameras in a period of 3 months (1208 camera days) we recorded over 2700 events. The methodology for estimation of wildlife species (European roe deer, red deer and wild boar) density are described in details in the EFSA report provided by Enetwild project (Enetwild consortium 2023).</p>
Data format	<p>Images and/or videos, numerical (number of observations), qualitative (behaviour, interactions).</p>

Description	<p>Camera traps are secured on a stable surface (usually a tree or a pole) to record wildlife passing in front of it, which trigger an infra-red sensor and the camera takes pictures or videos. Camera traps record date and time of the event but can also record temperature and atmospheric pressure. AI advancements have enabled automatic species recognition. Using the recorded data (images, videos) we can measure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species presence (species richness) • Activity patterns • Population estimates • Density • Behavioural data (on/off nests) • Human impact
Basic Literature	<p>Burton, A.C., Neilson, E., Moreira, D., Ladle, A., Steenweg, R., Fisher, J.T., Bayne, E. and Boutin, S. (2015), REVIEW: Wildlife camera trapping: a review and recommendations for linking surveys to ecological processes. <i>J Appl Ecol</i>, 52: 675-685. https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12432</p> <p>Ceasar, J., Milotic, T., Liefing, Y., Desmet, P., Jansen, P. (2019), Agouti: A platform for processing and archiving of camera trap images. <i>Biodiversity Information Science and Standards</i>. https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.3.46690</p> <p>Enetwild consortium et al. (2023) Wild ungulate density data generated by camera trapping in 37 European areas: first output of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW), EFSA supporting publication, 20(3): EN-7892. 90 pp. https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2023.EN-7892</p> <p>Sollmann, R. (2018), A gentle introduction to camera-trap data analysis. <i>Afr J Ecol</i>, 56: 740-749. https://doi.org/10.1111/aje.12557</p>
Contact person within the project	<p>Luka Duniš Elena Bužan</p>
Linked material	<p>https://wildlifeobservatory.org/ https://www.agouti.eu/ https://www.wildlifeinsights.org/</p>